

DESIGN OF WEB-BASED LEARNING SYSTEMMyo Ma Ma^{*1}Zarni Sann²Thi Thi Soe³^{*1, 3}Faculty of Computer Science²Faculty of Computer Systems and Technologies^{*1, 2, 3}University of Computer Studies (Mandalay), Myanmar^{*1}myomama.singaing@gmail.com²zarnisann@gmail.com³hlaing.nn@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

This paper intends to build a web-based learning system by taking the characteristics of learning agent. The system help user in the area of learning environments. The operation of the system includes the study courses of English Grammar and finally the students answer the question of English Grammar exam. Learning agent acting as a tutor to assist the students with specific learning needs, just like a human tutor or a classmate. This learning system is implemented with ASP.Net platform.

KEYWORDS:

English grammar, Learning agent, Web based learning

INTRODUCTION

There are many languages, among them English language is a global language. Four main classes can be categorized in studying English such as speaking, writing, reading and listening. Writing grammatically is important. In this paper, we present a web-based learning system in order to learn English grammar in [1]. The web-based learning system is designed based on the concept of learning agent [2, 3]. An agent is a computer system that is capable of independent action on behalf of it user or owners. Users can study the first level, second level, third level about the English grammar and they can know their grade by answering each level. Finally, the system produces the marks and the grade. In this way the learning agent can help some of the difficulties faced by the learners of English Grammar. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the several types of agents. In section III, we devote the design process to build the web-based learning system. Preliminary testing is carried out on the system, which is explored in section IV. Finally, we conclude the paper in section V.

METHODOLOGY

The agent program takes the current percept as input from the sensors and returns an action to the actuators. There are four kinds of agents' program are [2]:

Simple reflex agent

Simple reflex agents act only on the basis of the current percept, ignoring the rest of the percept history. The agent function is based on the condition-action rule: if condition then action. This agent function only succeeds when the environment is fully observable. Some reflex agents can also contain information on their current state which allows them to disregard conditions whose actuators are already triggered. Infinite loops are often unavoidable for simple reflex agents operating in partially observable environments [2].

Global-based agent

Goal-based agents further expand on the capabilities of the model-based agents, by using "goal" information. Goal information describes situations that are desirable. This allows the agent a way to choose among multiple possibilities, selecting the one which reaches a goal state. Search and planning are the subfields of artificial intelligence devoted to finding action sequences that achieve the agent's goals. In some instances, the goal-based agent appears to be less efficient; it is more flexible because the knowledge that supports its decisions is represented explicitly and can be modified [2].

Utility-based agent

Goal-based agents only distinguish between goal states and non-goal states. It is possible to define a measure of how desirable a particular state is. This measure can be obtained through the use of a utility function which maps a state to a measure of the utility of the state. A more general performance measure should allow a comparison of different world states according to exactly how happy they would make the agent. A rational utility-based agent chooses the action that maximizes the expected utility of the action outcomes—that is, the agent expects to derive, on average, given the probabilities and utilities of each outcome. A utility based agent has to model and keep track of its environment, asks that have involved a great deal of research on perception, representation, reasoning and learning [2].

Learning agent

A learning agent is a tool in AI that is capable of learning from its experiences. It starts with some basic knowledge and is then able to act and adapt autonomously, through learning, to improve its own performance. Unlike intelligent agents that act on information provided by a programmer, learning agents are able to perform tasks, analyse performance and look for new ways to improve on those tasks [2]. Learning has an advantage that it allows the agents to initially operate in unknown environments and to become more competent than its initial knowledge alone might allow. The most important distinction is between the “learning element”, which is responsible for selecting external actions.

A learning agent can be divided into four basic components [3].

Performance element: The performance element chooses what action to take. It later shifts to a new action based on feedback and suggestions for improvement. In our system, user can select first level, second level and third level.

Critic element: The critic element determines the outcome of the action and gives feedback. In our system, a typical feedback form consists tutorial results where students have to give a “Grade”.

Learning element: The learning element uses feedback and determines how the performance element should be modified to do better in the future. In our system, user can learn English Grammar Tenses.

Problem generator: That is tasked with developing new experiences for the learning agent to try. In our system, depends on the tutorial grade give suggestion for users.

SYSTEM FRAMEWORK

The simulation focused on the Unified Modeling Language (UML) as a tool for requirement specification and design. UML is an object-oriented modeling language using graphical notation for specifying, visualizing, constructing and documenting the analysis and the design phase of the system [4].

Use Case Diagram for Admin

Use case diagrams are excellent to describe the problem domain requirements and communicating with the system users [4]. The web-based learning system is designed using use case notation offered by UML. The UML use case diagram for admin of the system is shown in fig. 1.

Admin

Login: Activity that used for entry in the system

Update Lesson: Activity that used to add, delete, and update lesson with respective to level.

Update Tutorial: Activity that used to add, delete, and update tutorial exercise.

Logout: Activity that used for exist from the system

Fig. 1: Use Case Diagram for Admin

Use Case Diagram for User

Use case diagram for user of the system is shown in fig. 2.

User

Login: Activity that used for entry in the system

Learn Lesson: Activity that used to learn desired lesson with respective to level.

Answer Tutorial: Activity that used to answer exercises.

Logout: Activity that used for exist from the system

Fig. 2: Use Case Diagram for User

System Database

The web-based learning system has a database which is useful for entering data and viewing information to and from the database. The database is composed of following tables: student records, teaching courses for English grammar (tenses), question table, and grade table. Each table has its own operation and different number of fields. Example form of exercise is shown below.

QID	Question	Answer
1	I ——(get up) really early and practise for an hour or so most days.	get up
2	I ——(use) the Internet just about every day.	use
3	I ——(work) there since I was 15.	have worked
4	You ——(go) down to the traffic lights , then you turn left.	go
5	To start the programme , first you ——(click) on the icon on the desktop.	click
5	I ——(study) really hard for my exams.	am studying
7	My cousin ——(live) in Thailand at the moment.	is living
8	I ——(wait) for my friends.	am waiting
9	The price of petrol ——(rise) dramatically.	is rising
10	My mum's ——(say) I don't help enough.	always saying
11	He's ——(visit) exciting places.	always visiting
12	I ——(assume) you're too busy to play computer games.	assume
13	I ——(smell) something burning.	can smell
14	You ——(look like) your mother.	look like
15	Be quiet ! I ——(want) to hear the news.	want
16	The college ——(run) the same course every year.	runs
17	How ——(do) the burglar break in without anybody hearing him?	did

Fig. 3: Exercise Form

PRELIMINARY TESTING

After finishing the design phase, the web-based learning system is implemented by ASP.net [5] and preliminary observation is carried out. The system is intended for 2 levels of users with different right upon the data that can be stored, modified, or answer. Each user of the system must be filled identification requirements in order to login in its personalized interface and use the application and its feature. The system has three level to learn the English grammar (tenses). Each level has relevant lessons and tutorials. Admin can add, delete, update each level. Data entry form for admin is shown in fig. 4.

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Fig. 4 Interface for Admin

Registered user can be learned tenses, and answered the tutorial, and exercises with their appropriate level. Interface for user is shown in following figure.

Fig. 5 Interface for User

By answering the exercises and tutorial, the system notified grade level to user with message box. Figure 6 illustrate the answer form and notified message for third level user.

Fig. 6 Answer form and Message Box for Third Level User

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CONCLUSION

In this paper, design phase of web-based learning system is presented. This work intends to learn the tenses of English grammar through the online access by three level role. The process is based on the aspect of learning agent The presented system worked adequately throughout the preliminary testing. In the future works, the system can extend by including the remaining concepts of English grammar.

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